

Ichthyometric Indices and Growth Performance of *Clarias gariepinus* (Burchell, 1822)Exposed to *Anacardium occidentale* L. Nut Oil*¹Lelei, K. E., ²Eli, A. A. and ¹D. Okorharen¹ Department of Biological Sciences, Faculty of Science, Niger Delta University, Amassoma, Bayelsa State, Nigeria² Department of Environmental Management and Toxicology, Faculty of Science, Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State, Nigeria.**Article Information**

Article # 2005

Received: 9th Jan 20261st Revision: 7th Feb. 20262nd Revision: 18th Feb. 2026Acceptance: 17th March 2026

Available Online:

29th March 2026.**Keywords:**

Cashew nut oil,

Clarias gariepinus,

Growth parameters

Abstract

Anacardium occidentale L. (cashew) nut oil (CNO) is widely recognized for its antimicrobial and larvicidal properties and is increasingly used in fish preservation to extend the shelf life of processed fish. While this practice holds promise, concerns have been raised regarding its potential effects on aquatic organisms. This study investigates the acute toxicity and post-exposure growth responses of *Clarias gariepinus* fingerlings exposed to CNO. Fingerlings with mean length of 8.7 cm and mean weight of 4.94 g were exposed for 96 hours to 0, 4.0, 6.0, 8.0, and 10.0 ml/L of CNO, with a control (0ml/L). Some physicochemical parameters of the test media, fish mortality, survival rates, and the 96-hour LC₅₀ were determined. Survivors were transferred to clean water and reared for two weeks, after which ichthyometric and growth indices were assessed. Data were expressed as mean ± SD and analyzed using one-way ANOVA at P < 0.05. Results revealed concentration-dependent changes in the parameters, characterized by significant reductions in dissolved oxygen and pH, and increases in total dissolved solids and turbidity compared with the control. Mortality increased with concentration, with the highest mortality recorded in the 6.0 ml/L, the estimated 96-hour LC₅₀ was 35.79 ml/L. Survival rates ranged from 66.7% to 100% across concentrations. Post-exposure growth showed significant increases in length and weight, with the highest values observed in the 8.0 ml/L. Mean weight gain, specific growth rate, and Fulton's condition factor were highest at 4.0 ml/L. These findings suggest that while CNO may be valuable in fish processing and preservation, it has piscicidal potential if released into aquatic environments, highlighting the need for further studies on its ecological and health implications.

*Corresponding Author Eli, E.A: kariyelelei@ndu.edu.ng**Introduction**

Cashews (*Anacardium occidentale* L.) nuts are the fruits of the Cashew tree of the Genus: *Anacardium* and Family: *Anacardiaceae* (Anandhu *et al.*, 2023). This tropical fruit, native to northeastern Brazil was spread across the world during the Portuguese trade and is now cultivated in large scale in India, Vietnam and Ivory Coast. As at 2023, 3.9 million tonnes of cashew nuts were harvested globally, production was led by the Ivory Coast and India which made up 46% of the global production, Nigeria is also a major exporter of Cashews (FAOSTAT, 2025). The cashew fruit has pulpy and juicy flesh with sweet and flavourful taste; it can be fermented and distilled into alcohol while the kidney-shaped nuts can be eaten when roasted or dried; the milk

from the nuts serve as plant-based alternative to dairy milk. Other parts of the tree like the leaves, bark (that gives a yellow dye); the wood used in boat-making, house-boards, a source of charcoal, and other by-products, have been put to different uses (Andrade *et al.*, 2011; Carvalho *et al.*, 2011). The nuts of *A. occidentale*, rich in moisture, crude fat, crude protein, crude fibre and carbohydrate have been shown to be good source of oil and contain beneficial fatty acids like arachidic acid, behenic acid, lignoceric acid, linoleic acid, linolenic acid, myristic acid, oleic acid, palmitic acid, palmitoleic acid and stearic acid (Ogungbenle and Afolayan, 2015). The anti-nutritional and phytochemicals factors present in the nuts include tannins, phytate, alkaloids,

steroids, oxalate, triterpenes, glycosides, flavonoids and trypsin at very low levels (Akpotu *et al.*, 2021; Nwosu *et al.*, 2023). The testas of the nuts have been shown to contain epicatechin, catechin gallate, polyphenols, catechin, and procyanidin. The nuts, low in cholesterol; rich in vitamins and micronutrients; antioxidants (like lutein, tocopherols, zeaxanthin); anacardic acid, cardanols, cardols and inositol which are phenolic compounds have been shown to have diverse pharmaceutical, nutritional, therapeutic, culinary and cosmetic benefits; with anti-microbial- fungicidal, bactericidal, larvicidal, ovicidal and molluscidal; antiulcerogenic, anticancer and anti-malaria properties (Akinpelu, 2001; Lomonaco *et al.*, 2009; Morais *et al.*, 2010; dos Santos *et al.*, 2011; Voirin *et al.*, 2014; Hamad and Mubofu, 2015; Balasubramanian *et al.*, 2016; Taiwo *et al.*, 2017; USDA, 2018; Joseph, 2020; Sruthi and Naidu, 2020; Doniya and Ashoka, 2022; Araújo *et al.*, 2023; Anandhu *et al.*, 2023; Nyirenda *et al.* 2024; Jesse *et al.*, 2024; Aasa-Sadique *et al.*, 2025).

The oil extracted from the Cashew nuts have been shown to have insect repellent, ovicidal and larvicidal properties (Adedire *et al.*, 2011; Ferreira de Carvalho *et al.*, 2019), is now being used in fish processing and value addition- for the preservation and storage of dried fish, to extend the shelf-life, appearance and sensory qualities (Akpotu *et al.*, 2021). This has raised interests in its implication on fish and aquatic systems. In this study, *Clarias gariepinus* (Burchell, 1822) fingerlings were used to assess the effects of Cashew nut oil (CNO) on some Ichthyometric and growth indices of exposed fish, and by extension, aquatic systems.

Materials and Method

Test Organisms: Two hundred and forty *Clarias gariepinus* (African 'Sharptooth' Catfish) fingerlings of average length and weight of 8.7 cm and 4.94 g respectively, procured from a fish farm in Yenegoa, Bayelsa State, Nigeria. These were kept in holding in 50 L capacity plastic tanks for seven days using borehole water (Reish and Oshida, 1987), to acclimate to laboratory conditions in the Department of Biological Sciences, Niger Delta University, Bayelsa State.

The fingerlings were monitored for mortality and behavioural changes (with daily change of media) to allow for stabilization before exposure. They were fed with Coppen® feed of 0.8-1.2 mm pellet size at 5% body weight twice daily during the acclimatization period. There was no mortality during the holding period. These were used as the test organism.

Physicochemical Parameters of Test Media:

Some physicochemical variables of the test media (water) were analyzed to ascertain its suitability for fish survival based on the recommendations for the physicochemical parameters (APHA, 2005; Boyd, 2015) before and after exposure of the test organism to the Cashew nut oil (CNO). The physicochemical parameters analyzed were dissolved oxygen (DO), water temperature, total dissolved solids (TDS), pH and turbidity. These were measured *in-situ* using portable EXTECH Multi-probe (DO-700) meter, HANNA Turbidimeter (HI93414) and Hanna HI 9828 pH/ORP/EC/DO water analyzing device. Prior to and after taking of readings/measurements, all meters were calibrated with the appropriate standards to ensure accuracy.

Cashew Nut Oil : Cashew nut oil, assigned 'CNO' was the toxicant used for the study. CNO is locally produced (using cold extraction) and was sourced from Owerri in Imo State, Nigeria where the plant is commonly cultivated, but procured from a market in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State, Nigeria.

Range Finding Tests: Range finding tests were done to determine the threshold concentrations (concentrations at which minimum responses will be elicited from the exposed test organisms) so as to determine the exposure concentrations for the experiment. The threshold concentrations were predictive and incremental, adapted after Nwaogu *et al.* (2013), Hwa *et al.* (2016), Ferreira de Carvalho *et al.* (2019) and Okereke *et al.* (2020). From the findings, the exposure concentrations of the Cashews nut oil (CNO) were determined as 4.0, 6.0, 8.0 and 10.0 ml/L respectively.

Experimental Design and Acute Bioassay: This was a static toxicity test consisting of four exposure concentrations (4.0, 6.0, 8.0 and 10.0 ml/L) of the CNO and control (0 ml/L) made up to 12 L of borehole water of acceptable quality in plastic tanks in triplicates with ten test fish each. The experiment consisted of one hundred and fifty (150) fingerlings of *Clarias gariepinus* (African ‘Sharptooth’ Catfish) randomly allocated carefully into the four treatments (exposure concentrations) and control using Complete Randomized Block Design (CRBD). Being an acute bioassay, the exposure lasted for ninety-six hours.

During this period, the fish were not fed to prevent fouling of the test media by feed and faecal wastes. The water quality parameters-water temperature, dissolved oxygen (DO), pH, turbidity and total dissolved solids (TDS) of the test media were monitored at the end of this exposure phase.

At the 96th hour, the values of the fish mortalities based on concentrations were used to compute the mortalities, survival rate (SR %) and 96hr LC₅₀ of the CNO using Probit Analysis.

Grow-Out Period

Post-Exposure Measurement: After the 96-hour exposure to the different concentrations of the Cashew nut oil, the survivors were transferred to clean water without the CNO respectively, and

the fish were fed at 5% body weight twice daily for two weeks (at 9am and 4pm). The measurements of weight (in grams using a digital weighing balance) and length (in centimeters using a meter rule) of the test fish post-exposure were taken. The means values served as the initial weights and lengths post-exposure.

Feeding Regime and Growth Measurements:

The survivor fish which were transferred to clean water based on concentrations after 96hrs had the lengths and weights of the survivors taken weekly for two weeks and the mean values determined; having adjusted their feeding ration accordingly and fed at 5% of their body weight. They were fed with Coppen® fish feed (0.8-1.2 mm and 1.2-1.5 mm after weight adjustments) twice daily (9am and 4pm), to achieve optimum growth under experimental conditions while reducing feed wastes, toxic build-up due to unused feed or waste materials, prevent odour and opportunistic bacteria build-up. The lengths and weights were measured weekly and compared. The test organisms were regularly observed for any abnormalities.

Data Collection: The Survival rate (SR): which is the ratio of the number of the survivors to the total number of fish stocked per concentration (this indicates the survival of the fish during the period) was determined using the formula:

$$SR (\%) = \frac{\text{Number of individual fish at the end of the experiment}}{\text{Number of individual fish at the start of the experiment}} \times 100$$

The Fulton’s Condition Factor (K): which refers to the well-being of the fish (Ricker 1975), from the different treatments during the weeks of growth of the survivor fish were determined using the formula of Pauly (1993):

$$K = W \times 100 / L^3$$

Where: W= Weight of fish (g); L= Total length of fish

The weekly measured lengths and weights of the survivor fish from the different exposure concentrations were used to determine the growth performance of the fish post-exposure based on;

increase in length and weight; the mean weight gain (MWG); and the Specific growth rate (SGR), this is the measure of the daily growth rate of the fish during the two-week growth period from the different concentrations.

$$\text{Mean Weight Gain (MWG)} = FW - IW$$

Where: IL= Initial Length (cm) post-exposure; FL= Final Length (cm) after two weeks growth period; IW= Initial Weight (g) post-exposure; FW = Final Weight (g) after two weeks growth period.

Specific Growth Rate (SGR) were determined using the formulae by Bagenal and Tesch (1978) and Blackwell *et al.* (2000) as follows:

Specific Growth Rate:

$$\text{SGR (\%)} = \frac{\text{Log}_e W_2 - \text{Log}_e W_1}{T_2 - T_1} \times 100$$

Where; Log_e = Natural Logarithm of base e, W_1 = Initial weight of fish (g) in T_1 days; W_2 = Final weight of fish (g) in T_2 days;

Statistical Analysis: Data obtained were analyzed for mean and standard deviation of the measured parameters. One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to compare the differences in the means at the 95% ($P < 0.05$) confidence limit. SPSS[®] version 2.1 software was used for data analyses.

Results

Physicochemical Parameters: The mean values and standard deviations (SD) of the determined water quality parameters (temperature, dissolved

oxygen (DO), pH, turbidity and total dissolved solids (TDS) of the test media after the ninety-six hours exposure of the fingerlings of *C. gariepinus* to the 4.0, 6.0, 8.0 and 10.0 ml/L concentrations of Cashew nut oil (CNO) are shown in Table 1. These values were compared with the WHO (2008) and USEPA (2011)

Guidelines for water quality: From the results, the control (0 ml/L) had mean temperature of $27.93 \pm 0.24^\circ\text{C}$, pH was 6.75 ± 0.13 , DO was 5.43 ± 0.14 mg/L, TDS was 43.11 ± 1.89 mg/L, and turbidity was 54.66 ± 1.85 NTU. The mean values \pm SD of the physicochemical parameters in the exposure concentrations of CNO showed concentration-dependent variations in the parameters; especially a decline in DO and pH levels and increase in the TDS and turbidity levels with increase in the CNO, and when compared with the control which were significant ($P < 0.05$).

Table 1: Mean \pm SD of the Values of Some of the Physicochemical Parameters in the Test Media of Different Exposure Concentrations of Cashew Nut Oil (CNO) and Guidelines for Water Quality

Exposure Concentrations	Physicochemical Parameters				
	Temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$)	pH	DO (mg/L)	TDS (mg/L)	Turbidity (NTU)
Control (0ml/L)	27.93 ± 0.24^a	6.75 ± 0.13^b	5.43 ± 0.14^c	43.11 ± 1.89^a	54.66 ± 1.85^a
4.0 (ml/L)	28.90 ± 0.08^{ab}	6.45 ± 0.05^a	5.09 ± 0.00^b	48.11 ± 1.01^b	60.45 ± 8.44^{ab}
6.0 (ml/L)	28.97 ± 0.06^{ab}	6.33 ± 0.03^a	4.69 ± 0.18^b	51.45 ± 1.95^c	73.78 ± 7.03^b
8.0 (ml/L)	28.59 ± 0.86^{ab}	6.21 ± 0.02^a	3.89 ± 0.52^a	48.50 ± 1.30^b	73.55 ± 13.51^b
10.0 (ml/L)	28.51 ± 0.57^{ab}	6.11 ± 0.02^a	3.41 ± 0.77^a	47.59 ± 1.96^b	77.75 ± 9.03^c
WHO (2008)	<40	6.5–8.5	> 4	500	-
USEPA (2011)	-	6.5–8.5	-	500	-

Key: Means with the same superscripts down the columns are not statistically different at $P < 0.05$; DO = Dissolved Oxygen; pH = Potential Hydrogen; TDS = Total Dissolved Solids; WHO = World Health Organization; USEPA = United States Environmental Protection Agency

These values differed significantly ($P < 0.05$) with concentrations. The pH reduced slightly (6.45 ± 0.05 to 6.11 ± 0.02). DO levels in the exposure concentrations reduced from 5.09 ± 0.00 to 3.41 ± 0.77 mg/L, and were below the WHO (2008) guideline of 4.0 mg/L in higher exposure concentrations. The TDS values increased across the concentrations, with the highest level at 51.45 ± 1.95 mg/L in the 6.0 ml/L concentration, though, below the WHO (2008) and USEPA

(2011) limits of 500 mg/L. The turbidity values also increased (60.45 ± 8.44 to 77.75 ± 9.03 mg/L).

Mortality

Figures 1a and 1b show the mortalities of the fingerlings in the different concentrations of CNO (4.0, 6.0, 8.0, 10.0 ml/L and 0 ml/L) for 96 hours. The mortalities observed in the different exposure concentrations were time and concentration-dependent; mortalities increased with time and concentration and peaked in the 6.0

ml/L which had the highest mortality. Interestingly, mortality reduced in the 8.0 ml/L while no mortality was observed in the 10.0 ml/L which was the highest CNO concentration. The mortality plot for the lethal concentration (96hr LC₅₀) of the CNO based on Probit Analysis

(Figure 2) in this study gave an estimated 96hr LC₅₀ value of 35.79 ml/L. Which implied that, fifty percent (50%) of the test population will die at a concentration of 35.79 ml/L.

Figure 1a: Mortalities of *Clarias gariepinus* fingerlings in the Different Exposure Concentrations of Cashew Nut oil (CNO) with time (24hrs, 48hrs, 72hrs and 96hrs).

Figure 1b: Mortalities of *Clarias gariepinus* fingerlings from the Different Exposure Concentrations of the 'CNO'

Figure 2: Probit Plot showing the Lethal Concentration (96hr LC₅₀) of the Cashew Nut oil (CNO)

The survival rate (SR %) of *C. gariepinus* fingerlings in the exposure concentrations as shown in Table 2 were 100%, 96.7%, 66.7%, 93.3% and 100% in the 4.0, 6.0, 8.0 and 10.0 ml/L respectively. This indicated that the fingerlings in the 6.0 ml/L concentration had the lowest survival rate compared to the other exposure concentrations. The 10.0 ml/L concentration interestingly, had 100% survival rate like the control.

Growth Performance and Condition Factor:

The weights and lengths of the test fish after two weeks are shown in Table 2. The values of the lengths were 13.10±0.85 cm, 12.77±1.15 cm, 12.87±6.67 cm, 14.18±1.37 cm and 13.40±0.32 cm for the control, 4.0, 6.0, 8.0 and 10.0 ml/L concentrations respectively. There were significant increases (P<0.05) in the lengths of the test fish by the second week when compared with the post-exposure length. Generally, increase in length was not concentration dependent though, with fluctuations. The highest

mean length of 14.18±1.37 cm was observed in fish from the 8.0 ml/L concentration.

The mean weights increased significantly (P<0.05) at 48.77±15.75 g, 48.90±13.36 g, 47.47±7.77 g, 62.41±16.13 g and 48.27±1.63 g in the control, 4.0, 6.0, 8.0 and 10.0 ml/L respectively compared to the 46.63±10.77 g, 35.42±10.92 g, 34.27±2.92 g, 49.05±15.59 g and 43.37± 4.12 g post-exposure weights. These obvious increase in the weights were validated by

the values of the mean weight gain (MWG) of 2.14 g, 13.48 g, 13.20 g, 13.35 g and 4.90 g respectively; with the highest MWG in the 4.0ml/L concentration. These were reflected in the SGR (%) values of 8.08%, 10.61%, 10.15%, 9.79%, and 8.54% for the concentrations respectively; with the with the 6.0 ml/L treatment group exhibiting the highest SGR value of 10.66% (Table 2).

Figure 3: The weights (g) and lengths (cm) of *Clarias gariepinus* fingerlings in the Different Concentrations and Control at weeks One and Two of Growth

Table 2: Survival Rate (SR), Mean Weight Gain (MWG), Specific Growth Rate (SGR) and Condition Factor of *Clarias gariepinus* Fingerlings within Two weeks after 96Hours Exposure to Different Concentrations of Cashew Nut Oil (CNO)

Exposure Concentration (ml/L)	Number of Test Organisms	Survival Rate (SR %)	Post Exposure		Week 2		MWG (g)	SGR (%)	Condition Factor (K)
			Length (cm)	Weight (g)	Length (cm)	Weight (g)			
0	30	100	12.50±0.99 ^{bc}	46.63±10.77 ^{bc}	13.10±0.85 ^{ab}	48.77±15.75 ^a	2.14	8.05	2.21
4.0	30	96.7	11.55±0.80 ^{ab}	35.42±10.92 ^{ab}	12.77±1.15 ^a	48.90±13.36 ^a	13.48	10.61	2.35
6.0	30	66.7	10.80±0.23 ^a	34.27±2.92 ^a	12.87±0.67 ^a	47.47±7.77 ^a	13.20	10.15	2.23
8.0	30	93.3	12.73±1.61 ^c	49.05±15.59 ^c	14.18±0.37 ^b	62.40±6.13 ^a	13.35	9.79	2.19
10.0	30	100	12.83±0.25 ^c	43.37±4.12 ^{ab}	13.40±0.32 ^{ab}	48.27±1.63 ^a	4.90	8.54	2.01

Key: Means with the same superscripts down the columns are not statistically different at P<0.05; Number of test fish = 150

The Fulton's Condition factor (K) gave values of 2.21, 2.35, 2.23, 2.19 and 2.01 for the control, 4.0,

6.0, 8.0 and 10.0 ml/L respectively. The highest K value was for fish in 4.0 ml/L while the lowest K value of 2.01 was for the fish in 10.0 ml/L.

Discussion

The physicochemical parameters determined in the test media of the exposure concentrations showed concentration-dependent changes, when compared with the control. The pH and DO levels generally reduced with the exposure concentrations significantly ($P < 0.05$). The pH values were slightly below the WHO (2008) and USEPA (2011) Guidelines, implying slight increase in acidity. This was attributed to the acids (anacardic acid, cardanols, cardols and inositol, besides the diverse fatty acids) present in *A. occidentale* oil (Morais *et al.*, 2010; Voirin *et al.*, 2014; Hamad and Mubofu, 2015; Ogungbenle and Afolayan, 2015). The DO values in the concentrations above 4.0 ml/L reduced significantly with increase in concentration and were below the >4 mg/L WHO (2008) Guideline, indicating potential oxygen stress. These values suggested possible increase in the utilization of oxygen probably due to stress as a result of altered air-water interphase that would have facilitated the dissolution and availability of oxygen in the water column, attributable to the presence of oil film. The TDS values increased with increase in concentrations, with the highest level of 51.45 ± 1.95 mg/L in the 6.0 ml/L. These indicated the presence of soluble organic substances, though, these values were within the WHO (2008) and USEPA (2011) limit of 500 mg/L. Turbidity values showed increase with increasing concentration, from 60.45 ± 8.44 NTU in the 4.0 ml/L to 77.75 ± 9.03 NTU in the 10.0 ml/L, possibly due to the presence of particles. The values of the TDS and turbidity may be attributable to increased physiological activities of the fish, resulting in increased discharges into the water column; indicating possible stress on the exposed fish. Generally, the values of these parameters were within the WHO (2008) and USEPA (2011) limits, except for DO levels in the higher CNO concentrations, which dropped below the safe levels for fish survival. The abnormal behaviour of the test fish observed

during the exposure period such as, hyperactivity, erratic swimming with their tails vertically positioned, increased mucus secretion, and loss of equilibrium indicated systemic stress and exposure to toxic substances (Lelei and Sikoki, 2014).

Anacardium occidentale nut oil has been shown to have insecticidal properties, affects eggs laying capacity and is larvicidal against *Callosobruchus maculatus*, Cowpea weevil (Nwaogu *et al.*, 2013). It has ovicidal effect on *Musca domestica*, *Chrysomya megacephala*, *Anticarsia gemmatilis* and *Spodoptera frugiperda* as reported by Ferreira de Carvalho *et al.* (2019) and Nyirenda *et al.* (2024). It has eco-friendly algicidal and growth inhibition characteristics against *Microcystis aeruginosa*, *Oscillatoria tenuis* and *Chlorella vulgaris* as tested by Hwa *et al.* (2016). Anandhu *et al.* (2023), reported that, *A. occidentale* has antimicrobial effects against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Salmonella typhi*. With antifungal effects against the growth of organisms such as, *Epidermophyton floccosum*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Penicillium*, *Microsporium canis*, *Candida albicans* and *Aspergillus flavus* (Akinpelu, 2001; Jebapriitha and Karpagam, 2017). These effects were adduced to the anacardic acid contents of the oil. CNO toxic and mortality effects that were dose-dependent have also been shown in rats (Dias *et al.*, 2019; Okereke *et al.*, 2020). *Anacardium occidentale* nut oil has been shown from the findings of this study to have piscicidal effects on the fingerlings of *Clarias gariepinus* at concentration above 4.0 ml/L as evaluated in mortality rates for the different exposure concentrations with the peak mortality observed in the 6.0 ml/L concentration. The results indicated the toxic potential of CNO against *Clarias gariepinus*. Of note, mortality rate of the exposed fish peaked (33.3%) in the 6.0 ml/L concentration when compared to the higher concentrations of 8.0 ml/L and 10.0 ml/L. It could be said that, 6.0 ml/L was the concentration with the most observable effects on the fingerlings. The survival rate (SR %) of *C. gariepinus* fingerlings in the 6.0 ml/L exposure

concentrations of 66.7% which was the lowest, affirmed the latter. This indicated that the fingerlings in the 6.0 ml/L concentration had the lowest survival rate compared to the other exposure concentrations. The 96hrLC₅₀ value confirmed the toxic quality of the oil. The toxic effects of the oil on the exposed fish are likely due to the bioactive compounds present, especially the phenolics- anacardic acid, cardol, cardanol and inositol (Voirin *et al.*, 2014; Hamad and Mubofu, 2015) which are known to possess antimicrobial, ovicidal, larvicidal, insecticidal and other cytotoxic properties (Hwa *et al.*, 2016; Ferreira de Carvalho *et al.*, 2019; Okereke *et al.*, 2020; Anandhu *et al.*, 2023). These compounds amongst other phytochemicals present in the oil may interfere with essential biological functions in fish and other vulnerable aquatic organisms, with effects on the nervous, respiratory, osmoregulatory systems when released into water bodies.

From the growth responses of the test fish during the two week period after exposure, the lengths showed significant variations which were not necessarily concentration dependent. The highest length of 14.18±1.37 cm was observed in the 8.0 ml/L concentration, this was attributed to the individual responses of the test fish since they were of the same stock. Araujo *et al.* (2023), reported similar improved growth performance in Lambs fed with inclusion of Cashew Nut shell liquid in their diets at moderate levels. The mean weight gain (MWG) and SGR (that is, the measure of the daily growth rate of the fish during the growth period in the different concentration) values generally showed significant, concentration-dependent variations; the growth of the fish was allometric. The values suggested that, fish in the 4.0 ml/L concentration had the best growth responses at 13.48 g and 10.61% respectively, when compared with the other exposure concentrations, which were all better than the values in the control (2.14 g and 8.05% respectively). This implied that, the 4.0 ml/L concentration may have elicited the best performance in the fish. These values aligned with the assertion that, 'fish previously exposed, recover quickly, and it is profound at lower

concentrations (Ottoboni, 1991; Munzurul Hasan *et al* 2022; Lelei *et al.*, 2023). Since, chemicals when fed to animals at very small doses produce long-lived and healthier animals than the animals in the control (Frank and Ottoboni, 2011; Lelei *et al.*, 2023). This may probably be due to the fish's defense mechanisms being stimulated after being exposed to small quantities of xenobiotic, in this case, CNO. Which may have in turn, improved the fish health and performance post-exposure. This was apparent in this study as was seen in the findings. The test fish which survived exposure to the lower concentrations of CNO ended up performing better (as seen in the MWG and SGR values) than those in the higher concentrations and the control (Lelei *et al.*, 2023).

The Condition factor (K) used as an index of the condition or well-being of fish (Ricker 1975) and can be used to infer on the physiological condition and welfare of fish, and compare the wellbeing of fish (Seher and Suleyman, 2012). According to Blackwell *et al.* (2000), the condition factor of fish may vary among different species in different locations. For mature freshwater fish, Bagenal and Tesch (1978), recommended K value range of 2.9-4.8 as suitable. In this study, the values of the Fulton's condition factor (K) of 2.21, 2.35, 2.23, 2.19 and 2.01 were determined for the fish in the control, 4.0, 6.0, 8.0 and 10.0ml/L respectively. The exposed fish had higher K values than the control, though, all the K values were <3. These values indicated that, the fish were in 'good state' of health; considering that, the test fish were fingerlings and their potential optimum growth/maturity had not yet been attained (Angelescu *et al.*, 1958). The fish from the lower concentrations had better K values, with 2.35 from the 4.0 ml/L concentration as the highest K value. This, in line with the MWG and SGR values affirmed that the 4.0 ml/L elicited the most response or best performance (post exposure) from *C. gariepinus*. It could be inferred from this that, the concentrations triggered responses that allowed for 'good recovery' of the previously exposed *C. gariepinus*, especially in the 4.0 ml/L concentration. This was similar to the findings of Lelei *et al.* (2023). Generally, the K values were

comparative to other reports; Getso *et al.* (2017), reported K value of 0.516 for *Clarias gariepinus* (with 8.0 to 25.6 cm length and 16.7 to 97.5 g weight) in Wudil River, Kano State, Nigeria. Abanikannda *et al.* (2019), in their study showed that, *C. gariepinus* cultivated on a farm in Ojo, Lagos State, Nigeria had K value of 1.16 (with 12.02 cm length and 9.74 g weight). Joseph *et al.* (2019), reported K values of 0.764 (with 22.18 cm length and 87.03 g weight) for *C. gariepinus* in Calabar River.

The ichthyometric indices as determined in this study suggest that, there are potential ecological risks associated with the presence of Cashew nut (*A. occidentale*) oil in aquatic environments. Though, the elimination of the source of CNO can result in recovery of exposed fish with 'good health status', as observed in the growth performance post-exposure. *Anacardium occidentale* nut oil can have piscicidal effects on fish populations.

Conclusion

The study has by its findings on the ichthyometric indices shown that, *A. occidentale* has piscicidal effect on *C. gariepinus* fingerlings, reflected in the effects on the physicochemical parameters of the test media, the mortalities and survival rate of the exposed fish and the estimated 96hrLC₅₀ value. These have shown that, the inclusion of this oil in fish production, processing and preservation which may be value addition with respect to increasing the shelf life of processed fish and fish products. It also has its implications on fish survival in culture or in the wild, if the oil is discharged into aquatic systems. *These findings underscore the need for further research on the environmental safety of CNO, particularly in aquatic ecosystems where its use could have unintended consequences for local fauna*

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare that there is no competing or conflict of interest with respect to this study.

References

Aasa-Sadique, A.D., Abiona, M.A., Oladipupo O.A., Abejoye O.A., Adedokun, A.A. and O. O. Oladunjoye (2025). Bioactive compounds in

Anacardium occidentale and their role in antimalarial activity: A phytochemical perspective. *International Journal of Science and Research Archive*, 17(02): 766–772.

Abanikannda, O.T.F., Jimoh, A.A., Abagun, A.A. and L.A. Badmus (2019). Comparative study of growth parameters of African Catfishes as panacea for food security. *Nigerian J. Anim. Sci.*, 21 (3): 179-192

Adedire, C.O., Obembe, O.M., Akinkurolere, R.O. and S. O. Oduleye (2011). Response of *Callosobruchus maculatus* (Coleoptera:

Chrysomelidae: Bruchinae) to extracts of cashew kernels. *Journal of Plant Diseases and Protection*, 118: 75–79.

Akinpelu, D.A. (2001). Antimicrobial activity of *Anacardium occidentale* bark. *Fitoterapia*, 72: 286–287.

Akpotu, J. O., S. J. Oniye, S. A. Abdullahi and B. T. Magaji (2021). Comparative Organoleptic Assessment of Smoke-dried *Oreochromis niloticus* and *Clarias gariepinus* treated with *Anacardium occidentale* Nut oil. *Global Scientific Journals*, 9 (7): 1230-1252.

Anandhu P. V., Karthika, V. and R. Manju (2023). Extraction of Cashew Nut Seed Oil and Its Effects on *Staphylococcus aureus*. *International Journal of All Research Education and Scientific Methods (IJARESM)*, 11 (5): 987-993.

Andrade, T.J.A.S., Araujo, B.Q., Cito' A.M.G.L., Silva, J., Saffi, J., Richter, M.F. and A. B. F. Ferraz (2011). Antioxidant properties and chemical composition of technical Cashew Nut Shell Liquid (tCNSL). *Food Chemistry*, 126:1044 48.

Angelescu, V., Gneri F.S. and Nani A. (1958). Argentine sea hake (Biology and Taxonomy). *Secr. Mar. Serv. Hydrogenation. Nav. Public H1004: 1-224.*

APHA (2005). Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater. American Public Health Association. 21st ed. Washington, D.C.

- Araújo, D., M. Araújo, S. Silva, J. P. Filho, M. Parente, R. Oliveira, S. Mazzetto, J. Oliveira, R. E. dvan and L. Bezerra (2023). Effect of technical cashew nut shell liquid on growth, physicochemical and fatty acid composition of lamb meat. *Small Ruminant Research*, 227:107070. s
- Bagenal, T.B. and Tesch, F.W. (1978). Methods of Assessment of Fish Production in Fresh Waters. IBP Handbook No. 3 (3rd Ed.). Oxford Blackwell Scientific Publication, London. 136p.
- Balasubramanian, B., K. Sherfudeen, S. Kaliannan and K. Murugesan 2016. Cashew nut shell liquid poisoning. *Indian J. Crit. Care Med.*, 20 (57-58).
- Blackwell, B.G., Brown, M.L. and Willis, D.W. (2000). Relative weight (Wr) status and current use in fisheries assessment and management. *Reviews in Fisheries Science*, 8: 1-44.
- Boyd, C. E. (2015). Water Quality: An Introduction (2nd ed.). Springer International Publishing
- Boyd, C. E. (2017). Water quality and aquaculture. In: C. E. Boyd (Ed.). Water Quality: An Introduction (2nd ed., pp. 289-306). Springer International Publishing.
- Carvalho, A. L. N., Annoni, R., Silva, P. R. P., Borelli, P., Fock, R. A. and T. Mauad (2011). Acute, subacute toxicity and mutagenic effects of Anacardic acids from Cashew (*Anacardium occidentale* Linn.) in mice. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 135(3): 730-736.
- Dias, C.C.Q., Madruga, M.S., Pintado, M.M.E., Almeida, G.H.O., Alves, A.P.V., Dantas, F.A., J. K. G. Bezerra, M. F. F. Tavares de Melo, V. B. Viera and J. K. B. Soares (2019). Cashew nuts (*Anacardium occidentale* L.) decrease visceral fat, yet augment glucose in dyslipidemic rats. *PLoS ONE*, 14(12): e0225736.
- Doniya, K. and S. M. Ashoka (2022). *Anacardium occidentale* (Linn): A Brief Review. *Int. J. Pharm. Sci. Rev. Res.*, 75(1) 02: 6-9.
- dos Santos, T.D.J.A., B.Q. Araújo, A.M.D.G.L. Citó, J. da Silva, J. Saffi, M.F. Richter, A.D.B.F. Ferraz (2011). Antioxidant properties and chemical composition of technical Cashew Nut Shell Liquid (tCNSL). *Food Chem.*, 126: 1044–1048.
- FAOSTAT (2025). "Cashew production in 2023: Pick Lists from World Regions/Production Quantity/Year". FAOSTAT of the United Nations, 2025. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. Rome, Italy. faostat@fao.org
- Ferreira de Carvalho, G. H., M. L. Dos Santos, R. Monnerat, M. A. Andrade, M. Gonçalves de Andrade, A. Barbosa Dos Santos, I. M. D. Bastos and J. Martins de Santana (2019). Ovicidal and Deleterious Effects of Cashew (*Anacardium occidentale*) Nut Shell Oil and Its Fractions on *Musca domestica*, *Chrysomya megacephala*, *Anticarsia gemmatalis* and *Spodoptera frugiperda*. *Chemistry & Biodiversity*. Pp 64
- Frank, P. and Ottoboni, M.A. (2011). The Dose make the Poison: A Plain Language Guide to Toxicology. 3rd ed. John Wiley and Sons Incorporated. 284p.
- Getso, B.U., Abdullahi, J.M. and Yola, I.A. (2017). Length Weight Relationship and Condition Factor of *Clarias gariepinus* and *Oreochromis niloticus* of Wudil River, Kano, Nigeria. *Agro-Sci. J. Trop. Agric. Food Environ. Exten.*, 16 (1): 1-4.
- Gupta, S., Sharma, A. and Kumar, A. (2020). Natural compounds as eco-friendly pesticides: A Review. *Journal of Environmental Science and Health, Part B*, 55: 1-13.
- Hamad, F. and E. Mubofu (2015). Potential biological applications of bio-based anacardic acids and their derivatives, *Int. J. Mol. Sci.*, 16: 8569–8590.
- Hwa, S. K., Bo Gwan K. and Jin-Seog Kim (2016). Algicidal Characteristics of Cashew Nut Oil against Microalgae and Development of its Mixtures with Synergistic Effects. *Weed and Turfgrass Science*, 5(3):136-143.
- Jesse, I. A., Istifanus, T., Mafe, A. N., Oloninefa, S. D., Attah, F. and B. T. Targema (2024).

- Profiling Phytochemical Constituents and Antibacterial Efficacy of Ethanol Extract of *Anacardium occidentale* Linn (Cashew) Slender Branches. *Nigerian Journal of Microbiology*, 38(2): 7207 - 7214
- Joseph, A. P., Otong, B. E. and P.E. Asuquo (2019). Length-weight relationship and condition factor of different sexes of *Clarias gariepinus* and *Oreochromis niloticus* from Calabar River, South-Eastern Nigeria. *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*, 10 (8): 1076-1090.
- Lelei, K.E. and F.D. Sikoki (2014). Effects of Dispersed Bonny Light Crude Oil on Two Life Stages of *Oreochromis niloticus* (Linnaeus, 1758). *Trends in Applied Sciences Research*, 9: 480-484
- Lelei, K. E., Sikoki, F. D. and Onyeche, V. O. (2023). Growth performance and condition factor of *Oreochromis niloticus* (Linnaeus, 1758) after exposure to chemically dispersed Bonny Light crude oil. *The Zoologist*, 22: 22-30.
- Lomonaco, D., G.M.P. Santiago, Y.S. Ferreira, Â.M.C. Arriaga, S.E. Mazzetto, G. Mele, G. Vasapollo (2009). Study of technical CNSL and its main components as new green larvicides. *Green Chem.*, 11: 31–33.
- Morais, T.C., N.B. Pinto, K.M.M. Carvalho, J.B. Rios, N.M.P. Ricardo, M.T.S. Trevisan, V.S. Rao, F.A. Santos (2010). Protective effect of anacardic acids from cashew (*Anacardium occidentale*) on ethanol-induced gastric damage in mice. *Chem. Biol. Interact.*, 183: 264–269.
- Munzurul Hasan, A.K.M., Syed, R. F., S. M. Majharul, I., Morteza, H., Md Shahjahana (2022). Response and recovery of Nile tilapia exposed to diesel oil – Behavioral, hemato-biochemical and morphological changes of erythrocytes. *Toxicology Reports* 9: 549–555.
- Nwaogu, J., Yahaya, M. A. and Bandiya, H. M. (2013). Insecticidal efficacy of oil extracts of *Balanites aegyptiaca* seeds and Cashew nuts against *Callosobruchus maculatus* Fabr. (Coleoptera: Bruchidae). *African Journal of Agricultural Research*, 8(25):3285-3288.
- Nwosu, N. B., Okoronkwo, N. E., Onwuka, O. M. and T. U. Osuchukwu (2023). Phytochemical and Nutritional Compositions of Two Varieties of *Anacardium Occidentale* L. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*, 19(02), 966–977.
- Ogungbenle H. N. and Afolayan M. F. (2015). Physical and Chemical Characterization of Roasted Cashew Nut (*Anacardium occidentale*) Flour and Oil. *International Journal of Food Science and Nutrition Engineering*, 5(1): 1-7.
- Okereke, G., Okezie, E. , V. C. Ude, C. N. Ekweogu, V. O. Ikpeazu and E. A. Ugbogu (2020). Physicochemical characteristics, acute and sub-acute toxicity of Cashew nut shell oil in Wistar Rats. *Scientific African*, 8: e00391
- Oliveira, I. M., Silva, L. M. and Silva, M. R. (2019). Use of Cashew nut oil as a fish anesthetic: Efficacy and toxicity. *Journal of Fish Biology*, 95(3): 751-758.
- Ottoboni, M. A. 1991.” The Dose makes the Poison”: A plain Guide to Toxicology. 2nd ed. Van Nostrand Reinhold, New York, USA. 255p.
- Pauly, D. (1993). Fishbyte Section. Editorial. Naga, *The ICLARM Quarterly*. 16(2-3): 26.
- Reish, D.J. and Oshida, P.S. (1986). Manual of methods in aquatic environment research. Part 10. Short-term Static Bioassay. *Food and Agriculture Organization Fisheries Technical Paper*, (247):62.
- Ribeiro, L. P., Silva, M. A. S. and Silva, M. R. R. (2016). Cashew nut oil: A Review of its composition, Properties, and applications. *Journal of Cosmetic Science*, 67(2): 147-158.
- Ricker, W. E. (1975). Computation and interpretation of biological statistics of fish populations. *Bulletin of the Fisheries Research Board of Canada* 191:1-382.
- Seher, D. and Suleyman, C.I. (2012). Condition factors of seven cyprinid fish species from Çamlığöze Dam Lake on central Anatolia, Turkey. *African Journal of Agricultural Research* 7 (31): 4460-4464.

Sruthi, P. and M. M. Naidu (2023). Cashew nut (*Anacardium occidentale* L.) testa as a potential source of bioactive compounds: A Review on its functional properties and valorization. *Food Chemistry Advances*, 3: 100390.

Taiwo, B.J., Fatokun, A.A., Olubiyi, O.O., Bamigboye-Taiwo, O.T., Van Heerden, F.R. and C. W. Wright (2017). Identification of compounds with cytotoxic activity from the leaf of the Nigerian medicinal plant, *Anacardium occidentale* L. (Anacardiaceae). *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, (2017) 25:2327–2335.

USDA (2018). Nuts, cashew nuts, raw. FoodData Central, US Department of Agriculture.

<https://fdc.nal.usda.gov/fdc-app.html#/food-details/170162/nutrients>.

USEPA (2011). USEPA Regional Screening Level (RSL) Summary Table.

<http://www.epa.gov/regshwmd/risk/human/index.html>.

Voirin, C., S. Caillol, N.V. Sadavarte, B.V. Tawade, B. Boutevin and P.P. Wadgaonkar (2014). Functionalization of Cardanol: Towards biobased polymers and additives. *Polym. Chem.*, 5: 3142–3162.